

TEACHING HISTORY IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This scientific article analyzes the process of teaching history in the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its goals and objectives, educational content, and modern pedagogical approaches. It also highlights the importance of the credit-module system, innovative pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, and digital educational tools in organizing history education. Through the teaching of history in higher education institutions, issues regarding the formation of historical thinking, national identity, patriotic feelings, and the development of research competencies among students are addressed. Conclusions are provided on the current state of history teaching methodology and the prospects for its improvement.

Keywords: historical education, higher education system, teaching history, history teaching methodology, credit-module system, pedagogical technologies, innovative methods, historical thinking, national identity, patriotism, digital education, competency-based approach, scientific research, student competence.

In the context of modern globalization processes and the expansion of the information space, the scientific study of history, especially the development of historiography and source studies, is of particular importance. The large-scale reforms being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan further strengthen the necessity of modernizing the education system, improving the quality of scientific research, and providing objective and truthful coverage of national history. Historiography is an important field that studies the formation, stages of development, and scientific schools of historical knowledge, serving as a theoretical and methodological basis for the correct interpretation of historical processes. Source studies covers issues related to the identification of historical sources, their classification, critical analysis, and introduction into scientific circulation. The combination of these two directions is an important factor in the restoration of historical truth and the development of historical thinking.

It is known from history that the Uzbek nation has always had a strong passion for knowledge and its acquisition. For this reason, science and scholarship have long flourished in the region. In particular, even before the arrival of the Arabs, the local population possessed its own distinct knowledge and potential. Following the Arab invasion of Central Asia and the spread of Islam, it is commendable that representatives of the local population left behind a unique scientific heritage that would serve as a fundamental guide for the entire world. From the very first days of independence, the government has carried out numerous reforms to restructure education in the republic. Today, the scale of ongoing reforms to improve the education sector and enhance its effectiveness, as well as their results, have reached a significant level. In this regard, developing higher education is being prioritized as the most optimal way to achieve the development of not only other educational systems but also all sectors in the republic. Currently, all pedagogical and psychological scholars recognize the

following UNESCO definition as the most comprehensive for educational technology: "It is the use of a comprehensive approach in designing and implementing the entire teaching and learning process, which considers technical and human resources and their interaction".

Regardless of the field of study among the social sciences and humanities in higher educational institutions, historical sciences play a special role in the development of a student as a mature individual and a citizen with an active worldview, in the proper formation of thinking. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev also pays special attention to this issue. On June 30, President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a decree "On organizing the activities of the Public Council on the Modern History of Uzbekistan under the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan." This resolution was adopted "in order to increase the efficiency of coordinating the activities of scientific, cultural, educational, and public institutions and organizations in researching and teaching the modern history of the emergence and development of Uzbekistan's national statehood, preparing and publishing scientific, popular science, educational-methodological, and educational literature, strengthening and developing mechanisms for the integration of science with education and other social spheres, and forming profound knowledge of the country's history among youth, primarily students of general education schools, professional colleges, academic lyceums, and students of higher educational institutions". As a result of this decision, textbooks are being developed to ensure the transition of the subject "Modern History of Uzbekistan" as a subject for undergraduate programs.

In recent years, in order to improve and develop the quality of education in higher educational institutions, the use of new and modern pedagogical technologies by teachers to cover the full content of the subject and deliver knowledge at the required level is becoming a requirement of the times, as a result of the increased attention paid to students' specialized subjects, the number of hours of history subjects among non-specialized subjects is decreasing. Until now, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge. Such a method suppressed independent thinking, creative search, and initiative in students. Now it is time to organize the educational process based on modern lessons that meet the requirements of the updated curriculum and standards. In other words, there is a growing demand for teachers who take a responsible approach to organizing modern lessons instead of boring ones, possess professional knowledge and methodological skills, are responsible, have mastered interactive pedagogical technologies, and are capable of organizing education based on innovations. Therefore, the role and significance of modern teaching methods-interactive methods and innovative technologies-in the educational process of educational institutions are incomparable.

Knowledge and experience in pedagogical technologies and their application in education ensure that students acquire knowledge and mature skills. In the higher education system, the teaching of historical disciplines is understood as a process necessary to impart knowledge to students through historical material, educate them in the spirit of national independence, and fulfill the tasks of fostering love for the motherland, as well as the process of mental (internal) and educational (external) actions of teachers and students. How important is it to transfer the subject of history not only to undergraduate students majoring in specialized history but also to other non-specialized undergraduate fields? In recent years, as a result of reforms aimed at developing the higher education sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan, many non-specialized subjects have been removed, but it is history that remains in the curricula of non-specialized undergraduate programs in higher education. This situation is not only a process in our

country, but also in many developed countries, history is on the list of mandatory subjects. The inclusion of history in the list of non-specialized mandatory subjects dates back to the 19th century. It was in this century that history began to emerge as one of the main directions of compulsory and modern educational institutions. Initially, in the higher education system of European countries, it was taught mainly "for the purpose of developing national identity and educating an obedient person". The extensive and appropriate use of modern teaching methods in summarizing individual concepts and drawing conclusions to develop students' concepts of historical knowledge in history lessons is very effective in shaping their thinking. This is because the comparative study of historical data plays an important role in their logical thinking, understanding the essence of historical events, identifying the objective and subjective causes of the socio-political life of that period, improving skills and abilities, reviving historical events, and shaping their historical thinking.

Implementing an integrative mechanism to increase the effectiveness of teaching history subjects can lead to the following prospects: the management structure for educational quality within the learning process will be modernized; a healthy competitive environment among regional educational institutions and pedagogical personnel will be enhanced; the effectiveness of ensuring school graduates' transition to the next stage of education will improve, and the competitiveness of graduates will increase;

- the effectiveness of scientific research results will increase;
- a didactic-methodological system will be created for monitoring educational quality based on the psycho-pedagogical analysis of student development and for forming their creative and intellectual abilities in history;
- additional programs and a set of documents will be formed to identify and develop the student's personality, potential, and abilities.

Specifically, new concepts on the history of Uzbekistan have been developed, the activities of research institutes have been improved, and increased attention has been paid to modernizing the system of archives and museums. Clear tasks were defined for the preservation of historical sources, their introduction into scholarly circulation, and the support of young researchers. Furthermore, improving the quality of teaching historiography and source studies in the higher education system, strengthening the scholarly potential of professors and teachers, and implementing international best practices were also noted as important priorities. In this regard, expanding cooperation with leading foreign higher education institutions and creating modern curricula and literature have been identified as crucial tasks. Therefore, the development of historiography and source studies in the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan holds not only scholarly but also socio-political significance. This article provides a scientific analysis of the reforms in this area, the priority tasks set by the President, and their practical outcomes. Additionally, favorable conditions are being created for foreign students through joint educational programs, academic exchange projects, and grants. This serves to advance historiography and source studies on an international scale, facilitate the exchange of scholarly experience, and more broadly introduce the nation's history to the global scientific community. From a practical standpoint, the teaching of history in military educational institutions, particularly the introduction of elements of historiography and source studies, plays a crucial role in shaping the strategic thinking of officer cadets. Making decisions based on historical sources, analyzing past mistakes, and learning from them enhances the effectiveness of military command and management.

In conclusion, it can be said that scientific and theoretical approaches are of great importance for improving the quality and efficiency of teaching social sciences. By updating the educational process based on modern pedagogical concepts, activating student activity, and increasing motivation, it is possible to form profound knowledge and social skills in the social sciences. Learning from history does not depend on the past, but on the needs of the specific historical situation and historical conditions. Here, the general similarities of reality in the historical situation of the present are of great importance, as well as those that occurred in the past and from which conclusions can be drawn as historical lessons. According to Hegel, if there is no general proportionality, there is no reason to rely on the past. The entire past of humanity consists of memories, both pleasant and unpleasant, and lessons that illuminate the path of future generations and guide them along just paths. Over the years, they have become important conclusions that serve goodness and progress, peace and harmony.

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